

Credit: OpenAI, 2025

Policy Brief

September 2025

Shaping Futures in 3T: Tracking, Transitions and Tiers in Adolescent Identity Development

A policy perspective on how educational structures in Romania influence student identity, opportunity, and equity.

Compiled by Raluca D. Szekely-Copîndean, Daria Dodan, Renata M. Heilman, & Oana Negru-Subtirica for LEARN, from an original document (“Educational identity processes in adolescence: An analysis of longitudinal evidence and the role of educational systems” by Oana Negru-Subtirica). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17175781

Funding Acknowledgement

This Policy Brief was supported by the European Commission action HORIZON-CL2-2023-TRANSFORMATIONS-01 for the project LEARN (Longitudinal Educational Achievements: Reducing iNequalities), Grant Agreement 101132531.

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme HORIZON-CL2-2023-TRANSFORMATIONS-01 Grant Agreement 101132531 and co-funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) grant agreement numbers [10107302, 10092247]; and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

ABOUT THE LEARN BRIEF

Educational systems in most countries worldwide play a decisive role in young people's life trajectories by providing the contexts for certain educational experiences and by regulating the levels of autonomy students have in deciding who they will become professionally. The EU Horizon Project LEARN aims to comprehensively address sources of inequality that may be embedded in educational systems, shaping students' professional and personal development.

From a psychological perspective, investigating how students adapt to their educational contexts and the decisions they (can) make at critical educational transition points is crucial to understanding identity development. This LEARN brief presents a recent analysis of the role the educational system plays in shaping student identity development, focusing on the case of the Romanian educational system. The analysis was done by a LEARN team member and is available [here](#).

ABOUT THIS INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

The review focuses on **educational identity**, a psychological construct considered a core part of a person's personal identity (Crocetti, 2017). Identity development is conceptualized as a dynamic interplay between one's self-confidence in one's life choices (Commitment), actively reflecting about committing to a certain choice (In-depth exploration), and comparing alternative choices when the one made is no longer satisfactory (Reconsideration of commitment) (Crocetti et al., 2023, see figure below).

Image source: Crocetti et al. (2023, p. 167; reproduced with permission from the first author)

During adolescence, concerns about defining who one is are particularly salient, with significant changes in educational identity. Within the identity development theoretical framework, older adolescents (15- to 18-year-olds) were shown to have increased commitment and reduced reconsideration compared to younger adolescents (11- to 15-year-old) (Branje et al., 2021), suggesting that the former are more aware of who they are and commit more to their choices. However, longitudinal studies that allow for addressing changes across time have portrayed a more nuanced picture (Meeus et al., 2012), indicating that the differences in educational identity trajectories might be related to the particularities of the educational system where adolescents learn.

This is because as students, adolescents also need to make important decisions that can alter their career trajectories in the long-term. Different educational systems offer students varying levels of autonomy to make decisions about their educational trajectories (**educational tracking**), at key moments called **educational transitions**. This impacts their self-formation and professional outlook in the long-term.

The Romanian case conveys an educational tracking system that is largely based on academic performance, with the most important transition happening at the end of lower secondary school. Depending on their National Evaluation results, students can be more or less confident about their admission to a high school of their choice. This can reinforce existing **social inequalities**, as *students with lower educational achievement often have limited access to higher-quality educational resources and opportunities to reconsider their academic trajectories*.

KEY FINDINGS

1. The Role of Educational Tracking for Educational Identity

Romanian students are often placed in educational tracks early on, based on their academic performance. These placements are difficult to modify and can entrench *social inequality*.

Longitudinal studies have shown that Romanian students commonly exhibit an "undifferentiated" identity profile, with only moderate levels of commitment, in-depth exploration, and reconsideration, suggesting a *lack of strong educational identity development* (Timar-Anton et al., 2023). At the same time, high-achieving Romanian students showed stronger educational commitment, but often accompanied by heightened levels of self-imposed pressure and perfectionism, which may support achievement but increase stress (Negru-Subtirica et al., 2023).

2. The Impact of Educational Transitions on Identity Formation

In Romania, the academic transition from lower secondary school to upper secondary school is a high-stakes transition in which students commit to either an academic-bound or a work-bound track. This often limits students' abilities to explore alternative educational trajectories (Timar-Anton et al., 2023). Educational identity processes may mitigate the impact of such choices on students' educational autonomy. Particularly, Romanian students who demonstrate strong educational commitment and exploration tend to also report clearer vocational goals (Negru-Subtirica & Pop, 2018).

During the transition from lower to upper secondary school, social inequalities can infuse into students' choices, as students with lower performances can be placed in less prestigious tracks. Such an effect may generate discontentment with one's own educational path. Dissatisfaction with education was found to negatively impact vocational identity by affecting students' career goals, potentially leaving them uncertain about what career path to choose (Negru-Subtirica & Pop, 2018).

IMPLICATIONS: THE OPPORTUNITY

The examination of educational identity development offers valuable insights for both researchers and policymakers. Understanding how different levels of autonomy in educational systems affect identity formation can inform policies that emphasize the roles of student agency and importance of long-term success.

The integrative review underpinning this brief also draws insight from a comparative framework by contrasting results of longitudinal studies on educational identity in three different educational systems: Romania, the Netherlands and Japan (see Negru-Subtirica, 2024). Educational **tracking** and **transitions** are key structural features that shape student agency. Systems with rigid tracks and transitions (Romania, Japan) may guide students into commitments that may not align with their evolving interests and abilities. While more flexible systems (the Netherlands) allow for gradual consolidation of preferences, this can also gradually reduce the intrinsic need for further exploration after choosing a track early on.

1. Consider the Comparative Impact of Educational Tracking and Transitions on Adolescent Identity

Different levels of autonomy in educational decision-making can create both opportunities and constraints for students. Systems that offer greater flexibility - such as the Netherlands' more gradual (early) tracking and transitions - may better support identity exploration and adjustment. However, even these systems may pose challenges when tracking occurs at an early age, potentially limiting meaningful choice before adolescents have fully developed their interests.

In contrast, Romania emphasizes high-stakes transitions around mid-adolescence. While this can reinforce inequality, it also supports strong educational and vocational identity alignment among high-achieving students and clarifies the goals of less engaged students. Similarly, Japan's structured system fosters long-term academic commitment, and the prevalence of active identity searching may reflect deep engagement with educational choices.

Policymakers can draw from these varied models to balance academic structure with developmental needs - ensuring students are still benefiting from systems that support motivation, planning, and goal clarity.

2. Examine the Importance of Educational Identity in Shaping Academic and Career Success

Strong educational identity commitments are consistently linked to higher academic achievement and more clearly defined vocational goals. Longitudinal evidence from Romania and the Netherlands shows that students who are committed to their educational paths tend to perform better in school and develop a stronger sense of career direction.

At the same time, educational exploration, when appropriately supported, can facilitate more informed and meaningful academic and career choices. In the Netherlands, structured exploration before key transitions was found to enhance academic performance, while in Romania, commitment to education was shown to reinforce vocational identity over time.

Policies that foster both commitment and exploration while minimizing premature decisions can enhance student motivation, academic persistence, and long-term adaptability. Educational identity interventions, particularly those timed before key transition points, can be instrumental in helping students navigate choices that shape their futures.

RECOMENDATIONS

1. Research Recommendations

Investigate the Cultural and Systemic Influences on Educational Identity: Future research should continue to examine how educational identity develops within specific cultural, institutional, and systemic contexts. Cross-national comparisons - such as those between Romania, the Netherlands, and Japan - highlight how educational norms, values, and structural features (e.g., the timing of transitions) shape identity processes differently. This research can help identify culturally responsive strategies for supporting student development.

Prioritize Longitudinal and Developmentally-Timed Studies: There is a clear need for more longitudinal studies, given that they can provide high-quality, granular data on causal effects and potential mechanisms of change (Pollock, Salmela-Aro, & Symonds, 2025). Longitudinal studies can trace educational identity development across key life stages and transitions. Research is also needed to determine when and how interventions targeting parents, teachers, and students can be most effective. Studies that link identity development to academic achievement and vocational identity over time are essential for building an evidence base to support meaningful policy interventions.

2. Policy Recommendations

Having a government-supported, sustainable, national-level approach to longitudinal studies provides the necessary evidence to inform effective policies (Pollock et al., 2025).

Raise Awareness Among Parents and Teachers About the Importance of Educational Identity: Educational identity can foster student development. In adolescence, students reflect more on how school is meaningful for their sense of self. Hence, parents and teachers can support their educational exploration especially before key educational transitions, when students benefit most from adult guidance.

Implement Educational Identity Interventions Before Critical Transitions: School-level interventions could support students' identity development in the lead-up to major educational decisions - such as selecting an upper secondary school track or applying to university. Effective interventions may include guided reflection tools, mentoring programs, and decision-making workshops that align educational choices with students' evolving interests and goals.

CONCLUSIONS

This policy brief underscores the critical role of **educational identity** in shaping students' academic outcomes and long-term vocational development. Educational systems, through varying degrees of structure, expectations, and timing of key decisions, influence the way students explore, commit to, or reconsider their educational paths. Understanding and addressing these dynamics - particularly the impact of **educational tracking** and **transitions** - can help create more equitable and supportive educational environments that foster long-term student success.

By integrating findings from longitudinal research, policymakers and educators can better design systems that promote not only academic achievement but also psychological well-being, adaptability, and meaningful career preparation - ensuring that students are equipped to navigate a changing world with confidence and purpose.

NOTE

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

Branje, S., de Moor, E. L., Spitzer, J., & Becht, A. I. (2021). Dynamics of identity development in adolescence: A decade in review. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 31(4), 908–927.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12678>

Crocetti, E. (2017). Identity formation in adolescence: The dynamic of forming and consolidating identity commitments. *Child Development Perspectives*, 11(2), 145–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12226>

Crocetti, E., Albarello, F., Meeus, W., & Rubini, M. (2023). Identities: A developmental social-psychological perspective. *European Review of Social Psychology*, 34(1), 161-201.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10463283.2022.2104987>

Meeus, W., van de Schoot, R., Keijsers, L., & Branje, S. (2012). Identity statuses as developmental trajectories: A five-wave longitudinal study in early-to-middle and middle-to-late adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 41, 1008–1021.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-011-9730-y>

Negru-Subtirica, O. (2024). Educational identity processes in adolescence: An analysis of longitudinal evidence and the role of educational systems. *Child Development Perspectives*, 18(2), 97-103.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12504>

Negru-Subtirica, O., & Pop, E. I. (2018). Reciprocal associations between educational identity and vocational identity in adolescence: A three-wave longitudinal investigation. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 47, 703–716. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-017-0789-y>

Negru-Subtirica, O., Pop, E. I., & Crocetti, E. (2023). The complex story of educational identity in adolescence: Longitudinal relations with academic achievement and perfectionism. *Journal of Personality*, 91(2), 299–313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12720>

Pollock, G., Salmela-Aro, K., & Symonds, J. E. (2025). Cohort Studies, Child Well-Being, and Policy Impact: A Special Issue of the European Psychologist. *European Psychologist*, 30(3), 145–147.

<https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000560>

Pop, E. I., Negru-Subtirica, O., Crocetti, E., Opre, A., & Meeus, W. (2016). On the interplay between academic achievement and educational identity: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Adolescence*, 47(1), 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.004>

Timar-Anton, C., Negru-Subtirica, O., & Damian, L. E. (2023). The role of parental socio-economic status and perceived career-related behaviors in developmental trajectories of educational identity in adolescence: A four-wave study. *European Journal of Personality*, 37(6), 782–797. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08902070221150480>